

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ENTREPRENEURIAL LEADERSHIP BEHAVIORS OF SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS AND ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE

Mehmet Akif Helvacı¹ⁱ,

Yücel Özkaya²

¹Assoc. Prof. Dr.,

Uşak University,

Uşak, Turkey

²Teacher,

Evliya Çelebi

Anatolian High School,

Kütahya, Turkey

Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators and organizational culture according to the opinions of teachers working in primary, secondary and high schools in Kütahya city center and districts. This research is a descriptive relational study. The sample of the study consisted of 395 teachers working in 2018-2019 Academic Year in the city center and districts of Kütahya province. Sample was selected by means of realistic sampling method. The data were analyzed with SPSS 18.0 statistical program. Within the scope of the research, whether there is a relationship between entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of administrators and organizational culture and sub-dimensions; and how entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators predicted organizational culture and sub-dimensions were examined. According to the findings, it was seen that school administrators could explain the 43.5% of the organizational culture statistically significant in the sense of entrepreneurial leadership behaviors in general. However, according to the correlation test results, it was found that there was a statistically significant, positive and moderate but close to high level relationship between administrator entrepreneurial leadership behaviors and organizational culture. According to these results, entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators have a statistically significant effect on organizational culture and it was concluded that as the entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators increase the organizational culture level increases.

ⁱ Correspondence email: mahelvaci@yahoo.com, yclzky@hotmail.com

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1. Introduction

Rather than being based on a direct rule or command, organizations are social and multi-faceted structures where all employees interact, operate in emotional, logical and mutual dialogue. By nature, people are in dialogue with other people around them. However, a human being is an emotional entity that is susceptible to being influenced by other people and events in the work environment. Negative effects in the working environment can reduce the motivation of employees, and positive events have the effect of increasing motivation and tightly engaging in their work (Karaköse and Kocabaş, 2006). Within the organization, each individual contributes to the development and change of the organization in line with his personality and educational characteristics, such as his authority, abilities and knowledge, and if these contributions are kneaded with each other in a coordinated manner and the benefit of one individual's contribution to the other, an effective power is formed for the organization (Aydın, 2010; Toytok, 2014). The primary objective of each organization is to maintain its existence, to adapt to changing conditions and needs of society, and to remain at the top position against its competitors in the competitive environment. This process may be related to the formation of some cultural norms within the organization and the personality characteristics of the individual who is the manager in the organization and leadership and managerial behaviors that can have an impact on the employees of the organization. In this context, there is a need for, a strong organizational culture in order to meet the changing and developing needs of the society, and leaders who can adapt to the organizational culture that will contribute to the survival of this culture and to advance the institution further (Asuimiran, Bagheri and Pihie, 2014; Crow, Hausman and Scribner, 2002; Pihie and Bagheri, 2013; Toytok, 2014; Yalınkılıç, 2012). A lot of research has been done about organizational culture and leadership concepts from 1990s to today and various results have been put forward. The concept of organizational culture has been associated with many concepts of leadership and behavior and has been the subject of many researches. As a result of these researches, it is seen that organizational culture is a concept that shows the personality of the organization and directs the organization and it is said that the formation of this can only occur through the leadership behaviors of the organization managers (Toytok, 2014).

Also in schools as in any organization, school principals called managers or administrators need to increase the success of schools, to be able to keep up with innovations, changes and social developments, to be able to evaluate existing opportunities and they also need to gain effective leadership behaviors and to establish a solid organizational culture in order to cope with the difficulties and difficulties encountered and to ensure that teachers work in harmony with each other (Asuimiran et al., 2014; Lebusa, 2009; Xaba and Malindi, 2010). In the 21st century that we are in, school leaders are expected to lead effectively in rapidly changing social, educational and

organizational contexts (Goldring and Rallis, 1993; Murphy, 1992). In recent researches the concept of school reform has emphasized the need for a more inclusive and collaborative school management. In this context, more inclusive and collaborative school leadership will require principals to look deeper into the school atmosphere, to view events from a different perspective, to involve teachers in school development, and to implement consensus-building practices within the organization (Utash, 2017).

These changes in the expectations brought about by the age reveal the necessity of school leadership that can make significant developments in different aspects, take advantage of all opportunities and fully adapt to innovative approaches (Berglund and Holmgren, 2006; Lebusa, 2009; Xaba and Malindi, 2010). According to George Boggs (as cited in Utash, 2017), *“strong and creative leadership is of course important, but entrepreneurial culture should take over the institutions”*. According to Leithwood, Jantzi and Steinbach (1999), entrepreneurial leaders are important for the development of schools as learning organizations, and entrepreneurship inventories will be important leadership tools for schools of the future.

Schools differ from other government agencies in terms of their many structural and functional features, such as cooperation, team play and co-development. The formation of organizational culture in schools is more important than other state institutions. In addition to being able to act in harmony between teachers and school management, people who will act as school heads must have rational and leadership behaviors that can meet the needs of society in order to manage and direct this formation (Toytok, 2014).

According to Eyal and Inbar (2003), school principals have to choose effective school leadership rather than traditional management approaches. However, according to Pihie and Bagheri (2013), school principals have to have this leadership behavior because they cannot be successful in management without entrepreneurial leadership behaviors. It should also be supported in this regard (Vecchio, 2003). It appears that organizational culture and leadership behaviors play a major role in school development and change. There is a need for a solid school culture to provide the change and development required by contemporary society; effective leadership is needed for a solid school culture. In this context, it is necessary to investigate the effect of school principals' entrepreneurial leadership behaviors on organizational culture.

1.1. Entrepreneurial Leadership

Entrepreneurial leadership has become an increasingly needed type of leadership in all organizations (Ruvio, Rosenblatt and Hertz-Lazarowitz, 2010). This leadership behavior allows school principals to improve the performance of the school, to creatively solve problems that may occur and to seize new opportunities to use resources effectively (Gupta, MacMillan and Surie, 2004; Rae, 2007). Entrepreneurial leadership behavior can help leaders improve their own performance and creativity in addition to their positive impact on their personal characteristics (Chen, 2007). Entrepreneurial leaders have the capacity to develop innovative ideas, the tendency to explore new opportunities, the

desire to maximize organizational performance, the ability to face challenges, and the ability to influence people to be innovative (Chen, 2007; Fernald, Solomon and Tarabishy, 2005; Gupta et al., 2004; Thornberry, 2006).

Through entrepreneurial leadership skills, school leaders help each member of the team perform the best work, see the need for change in the organization, add exciting alternatives to traditional practices, and identify and eliminate key barriers. They also involve all school members in the process of organizational improvement and development (Peck, 1991). For all these reasons, entrepreneurial leadership stands out as the most effective and up-to-date leadership style that school principals and other organizational managers should possess (Lebusa, 2009; Peck, 1991; Xaba and Malindi, 2010).

1.2. Duties, Responsibilities and Changing Roles of School Principals

School principals are seen as education and training leaders responsible for the effective and efficient use of all resources for school goals, team spirit and management and representation of the school (MNE, 2013). As mentioned, school principals are not only those who perform their duties as a person who deals with the routine work and procedures of the school; it also includes entrepreneurial leadership skills, using all resources effectively and efficiently, creating team spirit and organizational culture, collaborating, demonstrating reassuring behavior, producing effective solutions to problems, taking precautionary measures, guiding teachers, evaluating technological opportunities in school, school they need to be leaders who are responsible for identifying their needs and finding opportunities to meet their needs, guiding and guiding school staff. For this reason, innovative managers are needed to meet the needs of change in a developing and changing world (Asuimiran et al., 2014; Fullan, 1991; Gündüz and Balyer, 2012; Schneider, 2002; Yukl, 1998).

All these reasons show us the need for school principals who can exhibit entrepreneurial leadership behaviors which are introduce innovative practices in schools, acting proactively against crises and problems, encouraging staff to work collaboratively, active in using the resources and take advantage of opportunities (Gupta et al., 2004; Rae, 2007; Thornberry, 2006). Research shows that school principals can improve entrepreneurial leadership knowledge and competencies through various courses and trainings. (Asuimiran et al., 2014; Drucker, 1985; Pihie and Bagheri, 2013). For all these reasons, it has become an urgent need for school principals to shape their responsibilities and roles based on entrepreneurial leadership in order to organize the innovation process in their schools and design a school as required by the age (Lebusa, 2009; Park, 2012; Xaba and Malindi, 2010).

1.3. Entrepreneurial Leadership and Organizational Culture

In recent years, leadership and organizational culture have attracted great interest from both academics and researchers (Ogbonna and Harris, 2000, Toytok, 2014; Utash, 2017). Schein (1992) observed that the concept of organizational culture and organizational

leadership are conceptually and functionally intertwined. According to Schein (1992), the founder of an organization creates an institution that reflects its values and beliefs in the process of organizational formation. As the organization evolves and time progresses, the culture created by the organization begins to have an impact on the leader and shape the leader's actions and style. As this dynamic process continues, leaders are influenced by organizational culture. Bass and Avolio (1993), summarizing this link between organizational culture and leadership by Schein, argued that the leaders of the organization shaped the culture and the resulting culture changed the behavior of the leader. They also emphasized that the relationship between these two concepts has become a constant interaction. Although the concept of entrepreneurial leadership can be put into many definitions and frameworks today, few studies have been conducted to understand and conceptualize the concept of entrepreneurship in education (Bergman, Rosenblatt, Erez and De-Haan, 2011; Borasi and Finnigan, 2010; Eyal, 2007; Eyal and Inbar, 2003; Heilbrunn, 2010; Xaba and Malindi, 2010). In addition, an operational and measurable concept for the entrepreneurship of school principals has not yet been defined (Eyal, 2007; Eyal and Inbar, 2003; Eyal and Kark, 2004; Yemini, Addi-Racchah and Katarivas, 2015). Therefore, there is a need to investigate the relationship between entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school principals and organizational culture.

1.4. Purpose of the Research

The aim of this study is to determine relationship between entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators and organizational culture. For this purpose, the following questions were sought:

- 1) Is there a relationship between the opinions of teachers on entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators and their opinions organizational culture and its sub-dimensions?
- 2) To what extent do opinions of teacher on entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators predict all of their opinions on organizational culture and its sub-dimensions?

2. Method

In this section, information about the research model, population and sample selection, data collection tool and data analysis are given.

2.1. Research Model

This study is a descriptive relational survey model because it is a study to explain the relationship of teachers' opinions on entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators and their opinions organizational culture. Descriptive relational survey model is a research model that describes the relationship between the variables that cause this situation and the degree of this effect and relationship (Kaya, Balay and Göçen, 2012).

2.2. Target Population and Sampling

The population of this research consists teachers working in the primary, secondary and high school types of the Ministry of National Education in the city center and districts of Kütahya City during the 2018-2019 academic year. School administrators, kindergartens, primary schools with integrated classrooms, guidance research centers, special education and training institutions, science and art centers were not included in the research universe because they were taken as restrictions. For this reason, the realistic universe was used as the kind of universe. Realistic universe; It is the universe that the researcher creates by taking certain constraints into account (Altunışık, Coşkun, Bayraktaroğlu and Yıldırım, 2005). As a result of the restriction, 407 schools and 6975 teachers working in primary, secondary and high schools in the same city constitute the universe of the research. Theoretical sample size chart was used in the calculation of the sample. According to this table, it is stated that the sample size required for 95% confidence level, $\alpha = .05$ significance level and 5% tolerance level will be at least 370 in the studies with 5000-10000 universe (Balci, 2011). For this reason, the sample of the study consists of 395 teachers who were chosen with easily accessible sampling technique.

2.3. Instruments for Data Collection

In this study, a 15-item 5-point Likert-type one-dimensional "Entrepreneurial Leadership of School Administrators Scale (ELSAS)" developed by Köybaşı (2016) was used to determine the entrepreneurial leadership characteristics of school administrators. In addition, in order to determine the level of organizational culture, developed by Terzi (2005), a 29-item 5-point Likert-type and four sub-dimension "School Culture Scale (SCS)" was used. Both on ELSAS and on SCS, the participants were given the right to respond "never (1), rarely (2), sometimes (3), mostly (4), always (5)". Both scales are five-point Likert-type scales. In these scales, the number of intervals ($5-1 = 4$) was found and the corresponding interval coefficient was calculated as $4/5 = 0.80$. In both scales, the 1st choice value is "1,00-1,79", the 2nd option value is "1,80-2,59", the 3rd option value is "2,60-3,39", the 4th option value is "3,40-4,19" and the 5th option value is "4,20-5,00". Means were interpreted with reference to these range values. The Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient for the reliability of ELSAS was calculated as 0.98; The KMO value calculated to show that factor analysis is interpretable was found to be 0.97 and the result of Barlett Sphericity Test was 6591.98. However, as a result of the confirmatory factor analysis applied to the data of ELSAS, it was found that it was a one-dimensional scale with a factor load of more than 0.40. Cronbach's alpha coefficient, KMO and Barlett values indicate that ELSAS has a high level of validity and reliability. In addition, Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient for the reliability of SCS was calculated as 0.87; The KMO value calculated to show that factor analysis is interpretable was found to be 0.93 and the result of Barlett Sphericity Test was 5556.62. However, as a result of the confirmatory factor analysis applied to the data of SCS, it was found that it was a four sub-dimension scale with a factor load of more than 0.40. Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient, KMO and Barlett values indicate that SCS has a high level of validity and reliability.

2.4. Data Analysis

SPSS 18.0 program was used to analyze the relationship and impact between entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school principals and organizational culture. The level of significance in analyzes was tested at .05 and the findings were presented in tabular form for the purposes of the study. Correlation (r) analysis was conducted to look at the relationship between entrepreneurial leadership behaviors and organizational culture and sub-dimensions. The independent variable of entrepreneurial leadership was taken as the predictive variable and the dependent variable of organizational culture and its sub-dimensions were taken as the predicted variable. Regression analysis was performed to see how much entrepreneurial leadership behaviors predicted organizational culture and its sub-dimensions.

3. Findings

In this section, findings related to the sub-problems of the research are given Firstly, at this stage of the research, the findings and comments are given about the first sub-problem, "Is there a relationship between the opinions of teachers on entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators and their opinions organizational culture and its sub-dimensions?" question. Pearson Correlation Analysis was used for the findings of this first sub-problem of the study. Correlation is a method that explains the relationship between two variables and its size, direction and importance. The Pearson coefficient is indicated by the symbol "r". The number "r" ranges from "-1" to "+1". Values approaching 1 indicate increased relationship strength. The value approaching +1 indicates the perfection of the positive relationship; approaching -1 indicates the excellence of the negative relationship. If the value is 0.00, it means that there is no relationship between these variables. Relationship level between 0.00-0.29 is low level of relationship; between 0.30 and 0.69, the relationship is moderate; 0.70-1.00 means that the relationship is high (Büyüköztürk, 2018).

In the correlation analysis, entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators and organizational culture and the sub-dimensions of task culture, success culture, support culture and bureaucratic culture are examined and the results are given in Table 1.

As seen in Table 1, there is a statistically significant, positive and moderate relationship between ELBSA and OCG according to the opinions of teachers participating in the research ($r:0,660$, $p<.01$). However, according to the correlation coefficient "r", it is seen that this relationship is almost above the middle level and close to the high level (between 0.30 and 0.69, the relationship is moderate).

Table 1: The Relationship between the Opinions of Teachers on Entrepreneurial Leadership Behaviors of School Administrators and Their Opinions on Organizational Culture and Sub-Dimensions

	ELBSA	TC	SC	SuC	BC	OCG
ELBSA	-					
TC	,547**	-				
SC	,698**	,591**	-			
SuC	,648**	,556**	,857**	-		
BC	-,071	,028	-,138**	-,173**	-	
OCG	,660**	,740**	,847**	,839**	,290**	-

**p<.001

(ELBSA: Entrepreneurial Leadership Behaviors of School Administrators, TC: Task Culture, SC: Success Culture, SuC: Support Culture, BC: Bureaucratic Culture, OCG: Organizational Culture General)

According to this, OCG increases as ELBSA increases. In addition to, when the relationship between sub-dimensions of organizational culture and entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators are examined,

- In terms of task culture (TC): There is a statistically significant, positive and moderate relationship between ELBSA and TC sub-dimension (r: 0.547, p <.01). According to this, TC sub-dimension increases as ELBSA increases.
- In terms of success culture (SC): There is a statistically significant, positive and high level relationship between ELBSA and SC sub-dimension (r: 0.698, p <.01). According to this, SC sub-dimension increases at a high rate as ELBSA increases.
- In terms of support culture (SuC): There is a statistically significant, positive and moderate relationship between ELBSA and SuC sub-dimension (r: 0.648, p <.01). According to this, SuC sub-dimension increases as ELBSA increases.
- In terms of bureaucratic culture (BC): There is a statistically insignificant negative and low level relationship between ELBSA and BC sub-dimension (r: -0,071, p >.05). However, the existence of this relationship is negligible. According to this, as the BC sub-dimension decreases albeit slightly as ELBSA increases.

According to these results, there is generally a medium level relationship between ELBSA and OCG and its sub-dimensions (except bureaucratic culture).

Secondly, at this stage of the research, the findings and comments are given about the second sub-problem, "To what extent do opinions of teacher on entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators predict all of their opinions on organizational culture and its sub-dimensions?" question. In this analysis, simple regression analysis was performed because of the predictive effect. If a single argument is used, these regressions are called univariate regression (Altunışık et al., 2005). The degree of force of the regression is expressed in R² and indicated by % (Büyüköztürk, 2018). For the data related to this sub-problem, firstly, the findings of the question that "To what extent do opinions of teacher on ELBSA predict all of their opinions on OCG?", then the findings of the question that "To what extent do opinions of teacher on ELBSA predict all of their opinions on sub-dimensions of organizational culture?" will be given.

Simple linear regression analysis was applied to the extent to which the ELBSA predicted the OCG and the results were shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Simple Linear Regression Analysis Results of the Entrepreneurial Leadership Behaviors of School Administrators Predicting the Organizational Culture

	B	Sd	Beta (β)	t	p
Constant	2,217	,086		25,764	,000
ELBSA	,359	,021	,660	17,428	,000
R ² = 0,436		R= 0,660			
R ² (Adjusted R ²) = 0,435		F= 303,748			

Dependent (Predicted) Variable: Organizational Culture General (OCG)

Independent (Predictive) Variable: Entrepreneurial Leadership Behaviors of School Administrators (ELBSA)

As seen in Table 2, it was seen that ELBSA were able to explain 43.5% of OCG in a statistically significant (Adjusted R²= 0.435, p <.01). In addition, one unit change in ELBSA leads to a positive change of 0.359 units on OCG (β : 0.359). According to the results obtained in this context, ELBSA, which are the predictive independent variables, affect the OCG, which is the predicted dependent variable, in a statistically significant and positive way. It was seen that ELBSA could explain 43% of OC level (R²= 0.435).

Simple linear regression analysis was applied to the extent to which the ELBSA predicted the sub-dimensions of OCG and the results were shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Simple Linear Regression Analysis Results of the Entrepreneurial Leadership Behaviors of School Administrators Predicting the Sub-Dimensions of Organizational Culture

Predicted Variable	Model	B	Sd	Beta (β)	t	p
TC	Constant	2,606	,123		21,257	,000
	ELBSA	,380	,029	,547	12,964	,000
				R ² = 0,300	R= 0,547	
				R ² (Adjusted R ²) = 0,298	F= 168,076	
SC	Constant	1,279	,139		9,193	,000
	ELBSA	,643	,033	,698	19,324	,000
				R ² = 0,487	R= 0,698	
				R ² (Adjusted R ²) = 0,486	F= 373,404	
SuC	Constant	1,494	,146		10,214	,000
	ELBSA	,590	,035	,648	16,870	,000
				R ² = 0,420	R= 0,648	
				R ² (Adjusted R ²) = 0,419	F= 284,595	
BC	Constant	3,226	,151		21,307	,000
	ELBSA	-,051	,036	-,071	-1,406	,161
				R ² = 0,005	R= 0,071	
				R ² (Adjusted R ²) = 0,002	F= 1,977	

Dependent (Predicted) Variable: Sub-Dimensions of Organizational Culture General

Independent (Predictive) Variable: Entrepreneurial Leadership Behaviors of School Administrators (ELBSA)

As seen in Table 3,

- In terms of task culture (TC): It was seen that ELBSA were able to explain 29,8% of the sub-dimension TC in a statistically significant (Adjusted $R^2= 0,298$, $p <.01$). In addition, one unit change in ELBSA leads to a positive change of 0,380 units on the sub-dimension TC ($\beta=0,380$). According to the results obtained in this context, ELBSA, which are the predictive independent variables, affect the sub-dimension TC, which is the predicted dependent variable, in a statistically significant and positive way. It was seen that ELBSA could explain 29% of the sub-dimension TC level ($R^2= 0,298$).
- In terms of success culture (SC): It was seen that ELBSA were able to explain 48,6% of the sub-dimension SC in a statistically significant (Adjusted $R^2= 0,486$, $p <.01$). In addition, one unit change in ELBSA leads to a positive change of 0,643 units on the sub-dimension SC ($\beta=0,643$). According to the results obtained in this context, ELBSA, which are the predictive independent variables, affect the sub-dimension SC, which is the predicted dependent variable, in a statistically significant and positive way. It was seen that ELBSA could explain 49% of the sub-dimension SC level ($R^2= 0,486$).
- In terms of support culture (SuC): It was seen that ELBSA were able to explain 41,9% of the sub-dimension SuC in a statistically significant (Adjusted $R^2= 0,419$, $p <.01$). In addition, one unit change in ELBSA leads to a positive change of 0,590 units on the sub-dimension SuC ($\beta=0,590$). According to the results obtained in this context, ELBSA, which are the predictive independent variables, affect the sub-dimension SuC, which is the predicted dependent variable, in a statistically significant and positive way. It was seen that ELBSA could explain 42% of the sub-dimension SuC level ($R^2= 0,419$).
- In terms of bureaucratic culture (BC): It was seen that ELBSA were able to explain 0,2% of the sub-dimension BC (Adjusted $R^2= 0,002$). However, this prediction was not statistically significant ($p > .05$). In addition, one unit change in ELBSA leads to a negative change of 0,051 units on the sub-dimension BC ($\beta=0,051$). According to the results obtained in this context, ELBSA, which are the predictive independent variables, affect the sub-dimension BC, which is the predicted dependent variable, in a statistically non-significant and negative way.

4. Results, Discussion and Suggestions

The main purpose of this study was to examine the relationship between entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators and organizational culture. The findings revealed that the school principal's entrepreneurial leadership behavior had a significant effect on the organizational culture of the school and that there was a relationship between entrepreneurial leadership behaviors and organizational culture. More specifically, the school principals' entrepreneurial approach, the amount of innovations applied and their positive outlook on events have a significant impact on the

development of culture and increase in culture in schools. Thus, it emphasizes the critical role of the principals' entrepreneurial leadership behaviors in encouraging and supporting the innovation process in schools. (Lebusa, 2009; Park, 2012; Xaba and Malindi, 2010; Yusof and Jain, 2009).

According to the findings of the study, when the relationship between entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators and organizational culture is examined, there is a statistically significant, positive and moderate but high level close relationship between entrepreneurial leadership behaviors and organizational culture. Accordingly, as entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators increase, the level of school culture increases. On the other hand, when the relationship between the sub-dimensions of organizational culture and entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators is examined, in line with the opinions of teachers participating in the research, it is found that there is a statistically significant, positive and moderate level between entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators and task culture and support culture dimensions; there was a high level of relationship between the success culture sub-dimension. Hereby, as the entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators increase, the levels of task culture, success culture and support culture increase. On the other hand, there is a statistically significant, negative and low level relationship between entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators and bureaucratic culture. However, the existence of this relationship is negligible. Hereby, as the entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators increase, the level of bureaucratic culture decreases, albeit slightly. In fact, this is an expected result. It can be said that bureaucratic culture is a culture that formalizes interpersonal relations and minimizes trust to each other. When the literature is examined, it is observed that these results are similar to the studies of Lesinger et al. (2016), Park (2012), Pihie and Bagheri (2013), Toytok (2018) and Zorlu and Tetik (2018). There is a positive relationship between leadership styles and organizational culture in the literature.

However, it was seen that entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school principals, which were considered as predictive variables in the study, could significantly explain the predicted variable organizational culture by 43.5%. According to the results obtained in this context, entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators affect the organizational culture in a statistically significant and positive way. Thus, it can be stated that as entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators increase, organizational culture level increases significantly. In addition, according to teachers' opinions, it was seen that entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators were able to explain, 29.8% of the task culture sub-dimension, 48.6% of the success culture sub-dimension and 41.9% of the support culture sub-dimension. On the other hand, according to teachers' opinions, it was seen that entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators were able to explain 0.2% of the bureaucratic culture sub-dimension, which is the sub-dimension organizational culture.

All these results show that entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators affect the organizational culture and sub-dimensions in general at high

rates. When the literature was examined, Pihie and Bagheri (2013) showed that the entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school principals improve organizational innovations and changes in schools and contribute to the development of organizational culture. In a study conducted by Park (2012), it was found that the leadership style of the school principal had a significant effect on teachers' perception of innovation in the school environment and school culture. Lesinger et al. (2016), in a study conducted by the school principals' entrepreneurial behaviors and instructional leadership and school culture revealed significant results. Thus, it can be said that the results obtained in our study are consistent with the results examined in the literature.

As a result, it can be said that entrepreneurial leadership behaviors of school administrators and organizational culture are two important factors affecting each other and there are significant relationships between these two concepts. In this context, there is a need for a strong organizational culture and entrepreneurial leaders to contribute to the survival and further development of the institution in order to meet the changing and developing needs of the society (Asuimiran et al., 2014; Crow et al., 2002; Pihie and Bagheri, 2013; Toytok, 2014; Yalınkılıç, 2012).

In line with the results of the research, the following recommendations can be made to the researchers; (i) The relationship and influence between entrepreneurial leadership and organizational culture can be examined by comparing private and public schools; (ii) Studies can be conducted on which leadership styles belong to school principals and to what extent these leadership styles direct organizational culture.

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